

MICROBIOLOGICAL AND CLINICAL ASPECTS OF VULVOVAGINITIS IN PREPUBERTAL GIRLS

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Abstract. Vulvovaginitis is one of the most common pathologies encountered in the practice of a pediatric gynecologist. The aim of the study was to determine the clinical and microbiological aspects of vulvovaginitis in prepubertal girls. The study included 24 girls with vulvovaginitis and 20 healthy prepubertal girls. The most common symptoms of vulvovaginitis were vaginal discharge - 87.5%, redness of the vulva - 83.3%, itching - 75%, burning - 66.6%, soreness - 62.5%; a combination of 2 or more symptoms was detected in 58.3% of patients. The vaginal microbiocenosis in prepubertal girls with vulvovaginitis was less diverse than in healthy girls. In the group of girls with vulvovaginitis, a higher content of *Streptococcus* spp., *Enterobacterium* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Sneathia* spp. / *Leptotrihia* spp. / *Fusobacterium* spp., *Mobiluncus* spp. / *Corynebacterium* spp., and lower levels of *Peptostreptococcus* spp., *Lactobacillus* spp., *Prevotella bivia* / *Porphyromonas* spp., *Megasphaera* spp. / *Veillonella* spp. / *Dialister* spp. and *Lachnobacterium* spp. / *Clostridium* spp were noted.

Keywords: vaginal and vulvar microbiocenosis, prepubertal girls, normal vaginal microbiota, vulvovaginitis in girls.

Introduction. One of the most common pathologies encountered in the practice of a pediatric gynecologist is vulvovaginitis. In prepubertal girls, there are many factors that contribute to the spread of infection in the vagina. One of the factors is a low level of sex hormones [5,12]. Before puberty, very little fat is deposited in the labia, there is no vaginal discharge, the mucous membranes of the vulva and vagina are very tender, and the proximity of the anus to the vagina and vulva is important for the development of infection [3,11,13]. In girls before puberty, the vagina consists of two layers - basal and parabasal, the vaginal epithelium has a neutral or slightly alkaline reaction (pH<4.5). The diagnosis of vulvovaginitis is made on the basis of complaints, clinical data, examination of the external genitalia and the results of a microscopic examination of discharge from the vulva and vagina. To determine the etiology of vulvovaginitis, clinical examination is not enough, since many vulvar and vaginal infections do not have specific symptoms, in this regard, laboratory and microscopic research methods are widely used, but, unfortunately, microscopic research methods cannot always determine normal and etiologically significant pathogenic microbes, since many types of microorganisms have similar morphotypes. The bacteriological method is more informative, but bacterial culture does not give a complete picture of the normal and pathogenic microflora of the vulva and vagina, since medical institutions do not have conditions for culturing anaerobic microorganisms, in addition, a significant drawback is the long cultivation period (4-5 days). PCR diagnostics of microflora is a modern research method, the test is based on quantitative and multiplex PCR in real time. The test allows you to determine the total concentration of bacterial DNA, the total bacterial mass and the concentration of microorganisms.

The aim of the study was to determine the clinical and microbiological aspects of vulvovaginitis of prepubertal girls.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted at the Republican Perinatal Center from 2022 to 2024. The study included 24 girls aged 7 to 13 years with vulvovaginitis. The control group consisted of 20 healthy girls of the same age. Exclusion criteria were the use of antibacterial drugs within 1 month before the study. All girls were examined only after obtaining voluntary informed consent from their parents. The average age of patients in the study groups was 9.7 ± 2.3 years and 8.9 ± 2.8 years. All patients underwent general clinical studies, including collecting complaints and a history of the child's disease from the mother, the mother's history of pregnancy and the postpartum period, breastfeeding, and a visual examination of the girl's vulvovaginal area were also studied. To assess the microbiological characteristics, materials for the study were taken from the lower third of the vagina. The material was collected using a sterile disposable urogenital probe inserted behind the geminal opening without special vaginal speculums and conductors, by scraping the parietal contents of the vagina on the right or left. The state of the vaginal microbiocenosis was studied using complex quantitative PCR with the «Femoflor» test systems. The absolute content of DNA of microorganisms in the vagina varied from undetectable to billions of copies, therefore, instead of absolute values, decimal logarithms (lg) are given. In addition to the types of microorganisms and groups of microbes detected by PCR analysis, the content of obligate and facultative anaerobes was calculated for each girl as the decimal logarithm of the sum of the absolute content of each group of microorganisms.

Results and discussion. The study of the anamnesis of mothers of girls with vulvovaginitis revealed that 11 (45.8%) had bacterial vaginosis during pregnancy, while in the group of healthy girls this disease was found during pregnancy in 7 (35.0%) women. Mothers of 13 (54.1%) girls with vulvovaginitis had an acute respiratory disease during pregnancy and took antibiotics, 4 (16.6%) women had hypertensive disorders, 9 (37.5%) had a threat of termination of pregnancy; however, when comparing these conditions with the anamnesis of mothers of healthy girls, no significant differences were found. In the group of girls with vulvovaginitis, deviations in birth weight from normal values (shorter than gestational age and larger than gestational age) were found 1.9 times more often than in the group of healthy girls (9-37.5% and 4-20%). In the group of healthy girls, 18 (90%) mothers breastfed their children, and in the group of girls with vulvovaginitis - 17 (70.8%). From the anamnesis of diseases in girls it was revealed that diseases of the urinary tract, as well as chronic tonsillitis, private ARIs in the group of girls with vulvovaginitis occurred 2 times more often than in the group of girls without the syndrome (5-25% and 12-50%). Allergy to food products was more common in the group of girls with vulvovaginitis - 8 (33.3%), compared with healthy girls - 2 (10.0%). Analysis of medications taken by the child showed that in the group of girls with vulvovaginitis every second 12 (50.0%) took antibiotics at least 3 times during 1 year, and in the group of healthy girls there were only 4 (8%). When studying the symptoms of vulvovaginitis in prepubertal girls, it was found that the most common symptom was vaginal discharge - 21 (87.5%), and vulvar redness - 20 (83.3%). Itching was noted in 18 (75%), burning in 16 (66.6%), soreness in the vulva was noted in 15 (62.5%), dysuria occurred in 8 (33.3%) girls. Adhesions of the labia were present in 5 (20.1%), and bloody discharge from the vulva and vagina was present in 4 (16.6%) girls. An unpleasant odor was noted in 6 (25%) girls. A combination of 2 or more symptoms was detected in 14 (58.3%) patients. The results of the study of the microbiocenosis affecting prepubertal girls are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Vaginal microbiocenosis in healthy girls and girls with vulvovaginitis of prepubertal age
(Relative content)

Microorganisms	Healthy girls			Girls with vulvovaginitis			p
	n=20*	%	M±m (%)	n=24*	%	M±m (%)	
Lactobacillus spp.	8	40,0	5,43±1,91	5	20,8	2,13±0,83	0,12
Enterobacterium spp.	6	30,0	4,17±1,48	11	45,8	8,96±1,81	0,04
Streptococcus spp.	6	30,0	1,88±0,35	11	45,8	6,36±2,15	0,04
Staphylococcus spp.	4	20,0	2,83±0,92	5	20,8	4,42±1,76	0,42
Gardnerella vaginalis / Prevotella bivia / Porphyromonas spp.	4	20,0	27,67±6,3 6	9	37,5	16,82±5,33	0,19
Eubacterium spp.	10	50,0	24,15±5,3 9	9	37,5	25,48±6,68	0,87
Sneathia spp. / Leptotrihia spp. / Fusobacterium spp.	5	25,0	4,74±1,84	11	45,8	8,31±2,96	0,31
Megasphaera spp. / Veillonella spp. / Dialister spp.	7	35,0	4,09±0,81	6	25,0	1,48±1,03	0,22
Lachnobacterium spp. / Clostridium spp.	12	60,0	2,21±0,77	9	37,5	1,65±0,56	0,55
Mobiluncus spp. / Corynebacterium spp.	13	65,0	4,62±1,29	10	41,6	8,34±2,81	0,23
Peptostreptococcus spp.	11	55,0	13,44±3,2 3	8	33,3	5,89±1,72	0,04
Atopobium vaginae	11	55,0	4,85±1,62	9	37,5	3,91±2,28	0,73
Mycoplasma hominis / Mycoplasma genitalium	1	5,0	0,21±0,03	1	4,1	0,22±0,06	0,88
Ureaplasma (urealyticum + parvum)	1	5,0	0,29±0,07	1	4,1	0,31±0,08	0,85
Candida spp.	7	35,0	1,38±0,34	5	20,8	2,48±0,52	0,08

• - the absolute number of girls in whom the microorganism was detected

In a study of the vaginal microbiocenosis in healthy girls and in prepubertal girls with vulvovaginitis, we found that at this age the vaginal microbiota of healthy girls is more diverse, while the microbial diversity of girls with vulvovaginitis was significantly lower. In the course of our study, it was found (Table 1) that in healthy girls *Prevotella bivia*, *Porphyromonas* spp., *Eubacterium* spp., *Peptostreptococcus* spp. predominated. In the group of girls with vulvovaginitis, compared with the group of healthy girls, a higher content of *Streptococcus* spp., *Enterobacterium* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Sneathia* spp. / *Leptotrihia* spp. / *Fusobacterium* spp., *Mobiluncus* spp. / *Corynebacterium* spp., and a lower content of *Peptostreptococcus* spp., *Lactobacillus* spp., *Prevotella bivia* / *Porphyromonas* spp., *Megasphaera* spp. / *Veillonella* spp. / *Dialister* spp. and

Lachnobacterium spp. / *Clostridium* spp. were established. If we take into account that obligate anaerobes represent a normocenosis for the microbial environment of the vagina of prepubertal girls, then a decrease in the absolute content of these microorganisms can be regarded as a marker of dysbiosis. According to many authors [1,2,5,6,10,13], in most cases (50-80%) in prepubertal girls, nonspecific vulvovaginitis is observed, in our study, all 100% of cases of vulvovaginitis in girls were caused by nonspecific microflora. In the study of Baka S, Demeridou S, Kaparos G. et al. [1] determined that vaginal discharge in girls bothers in 88.3%, genital erythema - in 66.6%, itching - in 59.6%, pelvic pain - in 34.6%, unpleasant odor - in 20.1%; Neyazi, Salwa Mohammed found the same symptoms [9]. Our study yielded comparable results: vaginal discharge was detected in 87.5% of cases, vulvar redness - in 83.3%, itching was detected in 75%, burning - in 66.6%, pain - in 62.5%, dysuria - in 33.3%, and unpleasant odor - in 25% of cases of vulvovaginitis in prepubertal girls. It should also be noted that in more than half of the cases, we noted a combination of 2 or more symptoms in patients. When studying the vaginal microbiota in girls, it should be noted that the microbial flora in girls with clinical signs and symptoms of vulvovaginitis is variable. There are still debates in the scientific community about what should be considered normal vaginal flora at different ages, and different, often contradictory data can be found in the literature. The vaginal microbiome is complex, and the presence of potential pathogens does not necessarily mean that they are responsible for the infection. In prepubertal girls, the vaginal pH is alkaline with a hypoestrogenic environment, which creates conditions for the growth of various microorganisms, most often of intestinal or oropharyngeal origin. In our study, we found that the vaginal microbiocenosis in healthy girls was more diverse than in girls with vulvovaginitis, in whom the microbial diversity was significantly lower. Similar data are noted in their works by Xiaoming, W., Jing, (2021) and others [13]. In our study, we determined that in the group of girls with vulvovaginitis, there was a higher content of *Streptococcus* spp., *Enterobacterium* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Sneathia* spp. / *Leptotrihia* spp. / *Fusobacterium* spp., *Mobiluncus* spp. / *Corynebacterium* spp. and lower levels of *Peptostreptococcus* spp., *Lactobacillus* spp., *Prevotella bivia* / *Porphyromonas* spp., *Megasphaera* spp. / *Veillonella* spp. / *Dialister* spp. and *Lachnobacterium* spp. / *Clostridium* spp. According to many authors [6,7,8], *Streptococcus pyogenes* (group A beta-hemolytic streptococcus) is the most common causative agent of vulvovaginitis in girls. In our study, we also noted an increased frequency of detection of *Streptococcus* spp. in the group with vulvovaginitis ($p < 0.04$), perhaps this is a consequence of frequent upper respiratory tract diseases in our patients, and therefore they are at increased risk of streptococcal vulvovaginitis, since this pathogen can easily spread to the genital area [4,13]. Many authors note an increased frequency of intestinal microorganisms in vulvovaginitis, such as *Proteus mirabilis* (14.4%), *Enterococcus faecalis* (12.2%) and *Escherichia coli* (7.0%) [1,2,4,8,9], in our study, comparable data were also obtained. The anatomical proximity of the vulva and anus, poor hygiene or improper hygiene habits in prepubertal girls may be the cause of vulvovaginitis and frequent detection of intestinal pathogens in vaginal discharge samples, but at the same time, there are studies that have shown that healthy girls have completely different vaginal and intestinal microbiota; in vulvovaginitis, the main pathogens were not of intestinal origin [13]. Thus, vulvovaginitis is the most common reason for referring girls to pediatric and adolescent gynecological services; further study of the etiology and course of inflammatory processes of the vagina and vulva in girls is a prerequisite for developing adequate and justified, taking into account

age-related characteristics, therapeutic measures and preventive measures to ensure the reproductive health of girls in later life.

Conclusions:

urinary tract diseases, chronic tonsillitis, acute respiratory viral infections in the group of girls with vulvovaginitis were found 2 times more often than in the group of girls without pathology;

the most common symptoms of vulvovaginitis were vaginal discharge - 87.5%, redness of the vulva - 83.3%, itching - 75%, burning - 66.6%, soreness - 62.5%; a combination of 2 or more symptoms was detected in 58.3% of patients;

vaginal microbiocenosis in prepubertal girls with vulvovaginitis was less diverse than in healthy girls;

in the group of girls with vulvovaginitis, there was a higher content of *Streptococcus* spp., *Enterobacterium* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Sneathia* spp. / *Leptotrihia* spp. / *Fusobacterium* spp., *Mobiluncus* spp. / *Corynebacterium* spp. and a lower content of *Peptostreptococcus* spp., *Lactobacillus* spp., *Prevotella bivia* / *Porphyromonas* spp., *Megasphaera* spp. / *Veillonella* spp. / *Dialister* spp. and *Lachnobacterium* spp. / *Clostridium* spp.

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